

THE STUDY OF IMPROVING THE STRENGTH CHARACTERISTICS OF NATURAL COTTON FIBER DURING MODIFICATION

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Abstract. This article examines the effect of water-soluble compositions based on sericin and polyethylene glycol on the physical and mechanical properties of natural cotton fiber. A positive change in the relative breaking load of cotton fibers treated with different concentrations of a polymer composition based on sericin and polyethylene glycol is given.

Keywords: cotton fiber, modification, composition, sericin, polyethylene glycol, wettability, physical and mechanical properties, recycling of industrial waste, strength, breaking load.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается влияние водорастворимых композиций на основе серицина и полиэтиленгликоля на физико-механические свойства натурального хлопкового волокна. Показано положительное изменение относительной разрывной нагрузки хлопчатобумажных волокон, обработанных различными концентрациями полимерной композиции на основе серицина и полиэтиленгликоля.

Ключевые слова: хлопковое волокно, модификация, состав, серицин, полиэтиленгликоль, смачиваемость, физико-механические свойства, переработка промышленных отходов, прочность, разрывная нагрузка.

Аннотасија. Ushbu maqolada seritsin va polietilen glikolga asoslangan suvda eriydigan kompozitsiyalarning tabiiy paxta tolasining fizik-mexanik xususiyatlariga ta'siri ko'rib chiqiladi. Seritsin va polietilen glikolga asoslangan polimer tarkibining turli konsentratsiyalari bilan ishlov berilgan paxta tolalarining nisbiy uzilish yukining ijobiy o'zgarishi ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: paxta tolasi, modifikatsiya, tarkibi, seritsin, polietilen glikol, namlash qobiliyati, fizik-mexanik xususiyatlari, sanoat chiqindilarini qayta ishlash, kuch, kuchlanish yuki.

An important place in the entire domestic textile industry is occupied by the manufacture of cotton fabrics. The textile industry is one of the most developed industries in Uzbekistan. The enterprises of the industry produce yarn, yarns, harsh and ready-made fabrics. The production of knitwear and sewing products has been developed: clothing and household products. The importance for Uzbekistan of the development of this sector of the economy is related to the following factors: the availability of its own raw material base of cotton (silk and wool); the textile industry is a labor-intensive industry, and, consequently, its development can contribute to solving employment problems and improving the standard of living of the population.

At the same time, combed yarn from medium-fiber cotton is increasingly being used in the production of textile products, successfully replacing yarn from long-fiber cotton.

The problems of increasing the technical level of production, improving technological processes and saving raw materials are fully faced by the textile industry and, in particular, by the cotton spinning industry, which processes natural expensive raw materials. Due to the fact that in recent decades the issue of environmental safety of finishing production has become acute, increased requirements are imposed on methods of intensifying finishing processes. It is necessary

that the intensification method preserves the structure and properties of the fiber as much as possible and is efficient and economical.

Today, solving technological problems related to the resources of raw materials and their processing is extremely important due to the growing needs of the world's population for products based on natural fibers.

The relevance of the work. Quality control involves checking the compliance of tissue quality indicators with the requirements of regulatory and technical documentation. The assessment of the quality level means the selection of a range of quality indicators, the determination of their numerical values, the selection of basic and the calculation of relative indicators. Of particular importance is the assessment of the quality level of the special fabric. In this case, the main indicator of the quality level of the fabric is its compliance with its purpose. According to the purpose of the fabric, certain indicators are selected to assess its quality. In addition, it is necessary to take into account the following indicators: operational, hygienic properties, aesthetic, technological, as well as fibrous composition and structure indicators of fabrics. The following indicators are used to determine the quality of silk fabrics :

Indicators for determining the quality of silk fabrics Table-1

The name of the quality indicator	The standard defining the norm of indicators	The name of the characterized property
1. Surface density (g/m ²)	GOST 3811	Fabric weight
2. Breaking load, N	GOST 3813	Tensile strength
3. The resulting nominal linear density of the raw material, tex	GOST 6611.1	The thickness of the thread, yarn
4. The number of threads per 10 cm, on the base and the weft.	GOST 3812	Fabric density
5. Width, cm	GOST 3811	Linear size
6. Resistance to abrasion along the plane.	GOST 18976	Wear resistance
7. Breathability, dm ³ / (m ² *s)	GOST 3816	Hygienic
8. Hygroscopicity, %	GOST 3816	Hygienic

During the operation of products, external influences (mechanical, thermal, chemical, etc.) are primarily exposed to the surface layers of materials, and the durability of products depends on their strength and durability. The use of polymer-composite technology, for example, in the textile industry, characterized by lower consumption of chemicals and less environmental pollution, makes it possible to reduce the severity of these problems.

The use of aqueous protein solutions to modify cotton fiber opens up new prospects for improving their hygienic properties. It has a number of advantages over spinning fiber using a mixture of poly alcohols and natural silk sericin at the stage of modification of a cotton polymer based on polymer-like transformations.

To improve the quality of natural cotton fiber, treatment with water-soluble composite solutions based on polyethylene glycol and sericin was applied.

Composite modification methods, or mixing methods, when polymer-compatible components or fine additives are added to the main fiber-forming polymer - carriers of new properties [1].

The purpose of this work is to improve the technological and operational characteristics of products made of cotton textile materials, possibly by modifying the mechanical and physical properties of the fiber. The aim of the study is to create effective modifiers based on sericin to regulate the properties of textile fibers.

The results obtained and their discussion. The effectiveness of the solutions of the created high-molecular composite modifier based on polyethylene glycol and sericin on the wettability of the fiber with water was compared with the similar effect of the solutions of the composition.

Taking into account the different size of the fiber diameter along the length, a study of the heterogeneity of the distribution by weight of the initial and modified cotton samples was carried out [2]. The effect of modification treatment on the mass values of polymer fibers with a minimum and maximum mass value in the initial state is presented in Table 1.

The weight values of cotton fibers before and after modification

№	polyethylene glycol		Weight change after treatment	sericin		Weight change after treatment
	Before completion	After processing		Before completion	After processing	
1	0,01351	0,013580	0,70	0,0134	0,01361	0,21
2	0,01342	0,013491	0,71	0,0133	0,01353	0,23
3	0,01302	0,013108	0,78	0,0132	0,01342	0,22

These tables show an increase in the mass of samples after modification, depending on the initial value and on the concentration of the modifier. The increase in weight is probably due to the inoculation of a small number of components of the compositions, modification of sericin in the processes of refining cotton fibers.

Figures 1 and 2 show the results of IR absorption spectroscopy of the studied tissues, indicating minor changes in the chemical composition of cellulose fibers after treatment with polymer compositions.

Fig. 1. IR spectroscopy of the initial fiber (after deformation)

Fig. 2. IR spectroscopy of the modified fiber (after deformation)

As a result of the modification, a breakdown occurs in the pores and capillaries with the formation of charged particles. The recombination of these particles on the surface of pores and capillaries leads to a compaction of the structure of cellulose fibers, an increase in their adhesion to each other, including between the components of the modifier, which helps to preserve the spatial shape of tissues.

Distinctive characteristics are observed in the spectral region at wavelengths up to 600 cm and related to various inclusions, and by the different intensities of the absorption bands of functional group residues, their different contents in each of the tissues can be judged.

The use of polymer-composite modifying technologies is possible at various stages of the production of fabrics and garments. The process of obtaining technical durable fabrics with improved properties includes modification of harsh fabric before finishing operations, which

allows to intensify thermal moisture processes, reduce the cost of finishing preparations and energy while reducing the duration of the technological process.

Thus, it is possible to explain the increase in the strength of cotton fiber samples treated with low concentration polymer solutions. At the same time, the polymer content in the modified fiber treated with solutions with a polymer composition increases relatively.

As a result of the modification, during the primary processing of cotton fibers, the technological process remains unchanged. In addition, studies have been conducted on the strength characteristics of the stability of the effect of modification of cotton raw materials over time, which indicate that after 1 year, the breaking load index does not deteriorate.

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